

SHORT NOTES

AQUO-AMMINO ANTIMONY CHLORIDE

BY H. K. DAS AND S. PANI.

Antimony chloride has been reported to absorb ammonia in molten condition with the formation of monoammino-, diammino- and triammino- antimony trichloride (Deherain, *Compt. rend.*, 1861, 52, 734). A saturated aqueous solution of antimony trichloride containing hydroxo-trichloro antimonite and aquo-trichloro antimony complexes has been found to react with suitable chelates or neutral molecules like pyridine (Pani *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 537, 538). It is therefore expected that ammonia would react with such a solution.

The chemicals used were of Analar quality reagents. Three different samples were prepared by slightly altering the conditions, as described below.

Compound (I).—A small amount of a saturated aqueous solution of antimony trichloride in a beaker was exposed to concentrated ammonia in a bottle inside a bell jar. Ammonia was immediately absorbed with the formation of a white compound. It was stirred from time to time and allowed to stand for over 16 hours when the whole mass became solid. It was powdered and repeatedly washed with ether, filtered and dried over sulphuric acid in a vacuum. The material when heated melts, and gives off ammonia and a white sublimate. It is very little soluble in water and the solution in hot water just responds to the tests of antimony and chloride. It is insoluble in ether but dissolves in sodium hydroxide with the liberation of ammonia.

Compound (II).—A small amount of a saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride with 25 to 30 c.c. of ether was exposed to ammonia as before in a bell jar. The reaction started immediately and the product obtained after four hours was washed, filtered and dried as before. The properties are similar to those of the compound (I). The analytical results are shown in the table below.

TABLE I

Compound.	% Sb.	% Cl.	% NH.	% HO.
Compound (I)	41.03	36.16	14.54	8.27
Compound (II)	43.42, 43.33	37.62, 38.04	11.91, 11.81	7.05, 6.82
Compound (III)	46.51, 46.45	40.54, 41.09	7.85, 7.87	5.1, 4.5
Calc. for				
$SbCl_3(NH_3) \cdot H_2O$	46.26	40.46	6.46	6.84
$SbCl_3(NH_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$	43.45	38.00	12.13	6.42
$SbCl_3(NH_3)_3 \cdot H_2O$	40.98	35.79	17.17	6.06

Compound (III).—A solution of antimony chloride in ether (containing no water) was exposed to ammonia as before and there was no evidence of the formation of any

solid compound even after four to five hours; only a very thin white film was observed on the side of the beaker. After 24 hours the solution became more dense, viscous and turbid, but there was no solid phase. No solid phase appeared even after 48 hours. After three days a solid separated out which was filtered, washed and dried as before. The properties of this compound were also similar.

Compound (I) is most probably $SbCl_3(NH_3)_3.H_2O$ with a small amount of the compound (II) which is $SbCl_3(NH_3)_2.H_2O$. The compound (III) is probably formed due to absorption of water besides the absorption of ammonia, and since the concentration of water vapour is small compared to that of ammonia inside the bell jar, the formation of this compound is slow. The complex (III) is therefore, $SbCl_3.NH_3.H_2O$. It is of interest to note that the complex (III), which is formed after three days, contains only one molecule of ammonia per atom of antimony, whereas, the other two, which are comparatively quickly formed under similar conditions, contain more ammonia. The ammonia and water molecules are strongly bound as they are not lost over concentrated sulphuric acid (the compound II when kept over sulphuric acid lost 0.03% in weight after three months).

These compounds are possibly co-ordination complexes.

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EFFECT OF AZOTOBACTER ON FIXED NITROGEN

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The utilisation of fixed nitrogen by *Azotobacter vinelandii* has been investigated by using a colorimetric method. It has been found that only those nitrogenous compounds are utilised by the bacteria which are likely to be reduced to ammonia, and that the lag period of the bacteria in case of compounds utilised increases with increase of concentration.

Horner (*J. Bakt.*, 1944, 47, 1) and Rosenblum (*ibid.*, 1952, 61, 475) investigated the effect of various nitrogenous compounds including amino-acids, amines, amides, glyco-coll, urea and hydrazine on the growth and nitrogen-fixing activities of azotobacter. They found that with the exception of urea these were not as readily utilised as the inorganic ammonium salts and nitrates.

Fuller and Rettger (*Soil Sci.*, 1931, 31, 219) observed that more complex organic compounds were not easily attacked by azotobacter and consequently the growth and nitrogen-fixing activity of the organism were not much influenced.

Lewis and Hinshelwood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 824) and Azim and Roberts (*Biochim. biophys. Acta*, 1955, 18, 363) have established that inorganic ammonium salts, nitrates and nitrites are utilised by *Azotobacter vinelandii*.